

Sentiment Natural Language Processing in Business Reviews

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Abstract

In this paper I have scraped over 50k reviews from Hello Peter using their Application Program Interface from different categories of business. I took reviews from 1-5 stars ratings from each business. The data obtained was used to build a Machine Learning Sentiment Model to classify sentiment of complex reviews.

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Sentiment Analysis

Defining Sentiment

Sentiment, sentimentality are terms for sensitiveness to emotional feelings. sentiment is a sincere and refined sensibility, a tendency to be influenced by emotion rather than reason or fact: to appeal to sentiment.

In this paper the *sentiment* we are tracking is *Negative, Positive and Neutral* text sentiment.

Features, Labels and Mathematical Presentation towards Approach

Sentiment and Data-set Explanation

Let X be the **Features** and Y be the desired **Labels**. For some X input we determine some output Y .

We have a set of records which we used supervised machine learning to create our data set.

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \vdots \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In our case i had a data-set of which i have generated from Hello Peter.

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} ReviewText \\ nReviewsPersonMade \\ RScore \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = [S_{Sentiment}] \quad (4)$$

I have extended the data-set into

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{Text} \\ S_{Positive} \\ S_{Negative} \\ S_{Neutral} \\ S_{Compound} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{Y} = [S_{Sentiment}] \quad (6)$$

Where $S_{Positive}, S_{Negative}, S_{Neutral}, S_{Compound} \in [-1; 1]$

Are generated from **Vader-Sentiment**

The $S_{Compound}$ score is calculated by summing the valence scores of each word in the lexicon, adjusting according to the rules, and then normalizing to a value between -1 (very negative) and +1 (very positive). increase. This is the most useful metric when you want a single, one-dimensional measure of sentiment for a given sentence. The term "normalized weighted composite score" is appropriate.

It is also useful for researchers wishing to establish standardized thresholds for classifying sentences as positive, neutral, or negative. Common thresholds are:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Positive}(+) & S_{Compound} \geq 0.05 \\ \text{Neutral} & S_{Compound} > -0.05 \ \& \ S_{Compound} < 0.05 \\ \text{Negative}(-) & S_{Compound} \leq -0.05 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The $S_{Positive}, S_{Negative}$ and $S_{Neutral}$ ratings are ratios for proportions of textual content that fall in every category (so those need to all upload as much as be 1... or near it with drift operation). These are the maximum beneficial metrics in case you need to investigate the context presentation of ways sentiment is conveyed or embedded in rhetoric for a given sentence. For example, exceptional writing patterns may also embed strongly nice or terrible sentiment inside various proportions of impartial textual content – i.e., a few writing patterns may also replicate a penchant for strongly flavored rhetoric, while different patterns may also use an extraordinary deal of impartial textual content whilst nevertheless conveying a comparable overall (compound) sentiment. As some other example:

Researchers studying statistics presentation in journalistic or editorial information would possibly preference to set up whether or not the proportions of textual content (related to a subject or named entity, for example) are balanced with comparable quantities of undoubtedly and negatively framed textual content as opposed to being "biased" toward one polarity or the alternative for the topic/entity.

R_{Score} is from the the Hello Peter data-set (*Review Rating as indicated in stars for 1-5*)

and $S_{Sentiment}$ is the output emotion where 0 = Negative , 1 = Positive, 2= Neutral

Problems with Reviews in Data-set

In *life* people can always be sympathetic, sarcastic, biased and unbiased.

The data-set contains some weird outliers. In few examples you will see what i am elaborating about.

1. This company is a joke, they are committing fraud. They take the peoples monies and return poor service. - The customer gives the business 5 stars.
2. This company is the best company ever - The customer gives the business 1 stars.
3. I failed to get hold of the company for several weeks but John Doe has helped me solve my problem give John Doe a raise - 3 stars
4. I have bought a laptop from ABC Traders, i had an issue where the laptop was overheating and decided to return it. ABC Traders are taking 3 months to issue my credit refund. What the hell am I going to do without any laptop for that time i use it for my business - 2 stars

As you see in the examples, there is some complex *corpus reviews* and also some customers do not know how to set the stars correctly.

All of this in the model is vital if we want to train our model to understand this complex corpus reviews. If we have an accurate data-set. Creating and training the model will be *chalk and cheese*.

In the next subsection I will introduce the method Supervised Machine Learning to correct our data.

Supervised Machine Learning

We have our data-set which we have computed using methods and techniques (will be shown below in notebooks)

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{Text} \\ S_{Positive} \\ S_{Negative} \\ S_{Neutral} \\ S_{Compound} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

For the Y label I have implemented a general solution to predict the sentiment. Such as:

Assigning the $S_{Sentiment}$ Score with a criteria based of the R_{Score}

Somewhat as defined in this schema and programming logic.

$$S_{Sentiment} = \begin{cases} 0(Negative) & \in R_{Score}[1;2] \\ 1(Neutral) & \in R_{Score}[3] \\ 2(Positive) & \in R_{Score}[4;5] \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Now we have a general data-set almost ready to be used for Machine Learning. We cannot use that defined data-set yet as we need to judge the sentiment by ourselves with human intervention.

We manually read each n row at the R_{Text} column and edit the $S_{Sentiment}$

Once all of that is manually moderated. We have a ready to use data-set! Which we can train for Natural Language Processing Sentiment Scoring.

In my case i experimented using the k-nearest neighbors algorithm (k-NN). I have achieved 80 percent accuracy based on training 50000 reviews as a starting point.

I have passed the following into the function.

$$f_{KNN}(R_{Score}, S_{Positive}, S_{Negative}, S_{Neutral}, S_{Compound}) = S_{Sentiment} \quad (10)$$

Our R_{text} gets converted into the $S_{Negative}, S_{Neutral}, S_{Compound}$ scores.

Using that our model have optimized the algorithm to handle our style text in reviews.

The more n records you have the better the model will become.

I designed a data-set from Hello Peter using their API system and pulled approximately 50000 records to train the model with. I believe that this model will understand the complex sentences and make good judgement into understanding sentiment.

If you want to take it a step further scrape all the reviews from Hello Peter and design this model.

Methods of Machine Learning

I have decided to use the following algorithms compared to a Neural Network because of cost and computing power and in production this would be faster to run.

1. **K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)** is a supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification and regression. It works by finding the k-number of closest data points to a new data point, and then classifying the new point based on the majority class of the k-nearest neighbors.

2. **Decision Tree Classifier** is a type of supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification. It works by recursively splitting the data based on the most significant feature and creating a tree-like structure. Each internal node represents a feature, and each leaf node represents a class. The algorithm makes a prediction by traversing the tree from the root to a leaf node.
3. **Random Forest Classifier** is an ensemble machine learning algorithm that combines multiple decision trees to improve the overall accuracy and stability of the model. It works by training multiple decision trees on different subsets of the data and then averaging or majority voting their predictions. Random Forest Classifier is often considered as one of the top algorithms for classification problems.

I have achieved the following results:

Algorithm	Accuracy
K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	0.8070565232847494
Decision Tree Classifier	0.8003910415926058
Random Forest Classifier	0.781016708140775

Table 1: Accuracy of different algorithms.

The parameters used will be shown in a different chapter in this paper in the source code section.

Prediction of Sentiment Scores In Action

Below is sample random data from the data-set in which the Sentiment Algorithm have converted the review text into a response.

1. **Review:** ADT Terrible ADT is terrible - poor and delayed service ... I installed the alarm in September ... they never responded even once to the alarm calls .. not even to check up... I asked for a cancellation a month later - within the first 3 month period .. they still have not actioned it .. now they telling me Ill have to pay penalty of R1800 ??? meanwhile I wrote a lengthy email of cancellation back in October explaining how they never even provided the service at all
I curse the day I ever though of having a relationship with ADT .. I am going to take this up .. I am not going to pay this amount
Predicted sentiment: negative
2. **Review:** I only play I only play
Predicted sentiment: positive
3. **Review:** Poor service delivery/products never arrived Poor service delivery. I placed and paid for my order online, and estimated delivery time was 4 - 5 days after payment. 2 weeks later I still don't have my products. Everyday delivery is cancelled due to some lame excuse. NB: I provided the correct delivery address and contact number.
Nobody from IG bothered to even make contact with me. I had to call them to check on the status of my order. . . everyday after 7 days passed. The responses I got were "your order is out on delivery", "your case has been escalated" , "we've scheduled an urgent delivery for you" . . and guess what, I still don't have my products!!!!
Frustrating!!! Now I have to switch over to another product. Thanks a lot IG for your unreliable service.
Clearly you don't take your service delivery and customers seriously. I cannot order facial products only to receive them after weeks! For this reason I will be cancelling my order and membership with IG . This has been a big inconvenience for me yet you expect me as your so-called "ambassador " to recommend your products to friends and family. There is no way I will ever refer anyone to use your products.
If anyone is considering using their products, just know that their delivery and collection services(which was another pain I experienced) will inconvenience you, big time.
Predicted sentiment: negative

4. **Review:** 2nd Premium increase this year I'm really not happy about the Miway increases. this is the 2nd increase on my premium this year. Some new items i had insured 3 months ago also increased.

How many times a year can i now expect increases, or does it depend on when you guys feel like it, or need bigger bonuses. The previous excuse was that the rand has weakened increasing the cost of spares thus the increase in premium. In the last few months the dollar has weakened, but no decrease, instead another increase with the same excuse.

Why do i have to threaten each time to cancel my whole policy in order to get a reduction?

Predicted sentiment: negative

5. **Review:** Great service The service was great , agents very professional and kind , informative and precise , and acted promptly and responded to all queries i expressed

Predicted sentiment: positive

Generating the Data-set

Scraping Hello Peter

- In this chapter i will be scraping the Hello Peter website for reviews of a specific company and just playing around with the legacy SentimentIntensityAnalyzer using their recommended threshold and parameters as denoted by the equation below.

$$\begin{cases} \textit{Positive}(+) & S_{Compound} \geq 0.05 \\ \textit{Neutral} & S_{Compound} > -0.05 \ \& \ S_{Compound} < 0.05 \\ \textit{Negative}(-) & S_{Compound} \leq -0.05 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Consider a company name on Hello Peter

- Telkom

Discovering from the website `helloworld.com` it uses a microservice architecture. The reviews are stored in a database and the website is just a frontend to the database. There is a normal website hosting the frontend and a separate website hosting the API.

The API is hosted on `api.helloworld.com` and the frontend is hosted on `helloworld.com`

Therefore running web diagnostics on the API will give us the information we need.

I have reversed engineered the API. To get reviews for a specific company you need to make a **GET** request to the following endpoint:

```
https://api.helloworld.com/consumer/business/<companynamewithdash>/reviews?page=<pagenumber>
```

Quite interesting to note that the company name is in the URL and not in the query parameters.

Anyway our life is easy now. We just need to make a **GET** request to the endpoint and we will get the reviews for the company.

- Telkom

```
https://api.helloworld.com/consumer/business/telkom/reviews?page=1
to get the first page of reviews
...
...
https://api.helloworld.com/consumer/business/telkom/reviews?page=n
to get the nth page of reviews
```

Before we start

Basic imports

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import requests # for making http requests
import json # for parsing json data
```

General Solution

I am making a function to get the reviews for a specific company. The function will take in the company name and the number of pages to scrape.

```
def GetReviews(companyname, pageno):
    # convert company name where spaces are replaced with hyphens
    df = pd.DataFrame()
    companyname=companyname.replace(" ", "-")
    url = 'https://api.hellopeter.com/consumer/business/'+companyname+'/reviews?page='+str(1)
    page = requests.get(url)
    jsondata=json.loads(page.text)
    last_page=jsondata['last_page']
    df = df.from_records(jsondata['data'])
    i = 1

    while i <= last_page:
        if pageno == 0:
            print("Processing page: "+str(i)+ " of "+str(last_page))
            pass
        else:
            print("Processing page: "+str(i)+ " of "+str(pageno))
            if i == pageno:
                break

        i = i + 1
        url = 'https://api.hellopeter.com/consumer/business/'+companyname+'/reviews?page='+str(i)
        page = requests.get(url)
        jsondata=json.loads(page.text)
        df = pd.concat([df,df.from_records(jsondata['data'])])

    return df
```

ill just do 100 pages for now

```
df = GetReviews("telkom",100)
```

```
df.head()
```

	id	user_id	created_at	\
0	4220709	189b4210-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188	2022-12-11 10:44:36	
1	4220657	2ab58790-5e1c-11ea-84a8-633da5152604	2022-12-11 08:21:07	
2	4220589	30c06500-2db3-11ed-9a2e-37d9f06d41d3	2022-12-10 23:51:47	
3	4220221	fb1cc90-f7d5-11e8-981e-d16280a3bb5a	2022-12-10 11:41:54	
4	4220027	f1989af0-247d-11ed-9b4a-437238555a96	2022-12-10 07:25:59	

	authorDisplayName	author	authorAvatar	\
0	michael	michael		
1	Tintswalo M	Tintswalo M		
2	Lulama R	Lulama R		
3	Moosa M	Moosa M		
4	Johanna B	Johanna B		

	author_id	\
0	189b4210-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188	
1	2ab58790-5e1c-11ea-84a8-633da5152604	
2	30c06500-2db3-11ed-9a2e-37d9f06d41d3	
3	fb1cc90-f7d5-11e8-981e-d16280a3bb5a	
4	f1989af0-247d-11ed-9b4a-437238555a96	

```

                review_title  review_rating  \
0                Telkom eish                1
1                Bad service                1
2  Telkom (9570 Rand To Terminate A ConTract)  1
3                Telkom sucks                1
4                BEST TELKOM EMPLOYEE        5

                review_content  ...  industry_name  \
0  We upgraded our Telkom LTE to uncapped a few m...  ...  Telecommunications
1  I use Adsl and I haven't had connectivity from...  ...  Telecommunications
2  They are Telling Me To Pay R9570 To Cancel A C...  ...  Telecommunications
3  Trying to resolve a billing issue with telkom...  ...  Telecommunications
4  I am writing this as one very happy (now ex-) ...  ...  Telecommunications

    industry_slug  status_id  nps_rating  source  is_reported  \
0  telecommunications      1         NaN  WEBSITE      False
1  telecommunications      1         NaN  WEBSITE      False
2  telecommunications      1         NaN  WEBSITE      False
3  telecommunications      1         NaN  WEBSITE      False
4  telecommunications      1         NaN  WEBSITE      False

    business_reporting  author_created_date  author_total_reviews_count  \
0                None          2014-02-03                2
1                None          2020-03-04                9
2                None          2022-09-06                4
3                None          2018-12-04                2
4                None          2022-08-25                2

    attachments
0                []
1                []
2                []
3                []
4                []

```

[5 rows x 27 columns]

Lets check shape of the data

```
# shape of the data frame
```

```
df.shape
```

```
(1100, 27)
```

Saving data for future use

```
# make a directory to store the data
```

```
import os
```

```
try:
```

```
    os.mkdir("data")
```

```
except:
```

```
    pass
```

```
# save the data frame to a csv file
```

```
df.to_csv("data/telkom.csv", index=False)
```

Evaluation of Business Reviews

```
from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
sentiment = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()
```

```
# iterate over the data frame
```

```
for index, row in df.iterrows():
    currentReview = row['review_title']+'\n'+row['review_content']
    sentimentScore = sentiment.polarity_scores(currentReview)
    df.loc[index, 'compound'] = sentimentScore['compound']
    df.loc[index, 'neg'] = sentimentScore['neg']
    df.loc[index, 'neu'] = sentimentScore['neu']
    df.loc[index, 'pos'] = sentimentScore['pos']
```

```
for index, row in df.iterrows():
    if row['compound'] >= 0.05:
        df.loc[index, 'sentiment'] = 'positive'
    elif row['compound'] <= -0.05:
        df.loc[index, 'sentiment'] = 'negative'
    else:
        df.loc[index, 'sentiment'] = 'neutral'
```

```
# count the number of positive, negative and neutral reviews
```

```
print(df['sentiment'].value_counts())
```

```
# print percentage of positive, negative and neutral reviews
```

```
print(df['sentiment'].value_counts(normalize=True))
```

```
negative    1100
```

```
Name: sentiment, dtype: int64
```

```
negative     1.0
```

```
Name: sentiment, dtype: float64
```

```
      id      user_id      created_at \
0  4220709  189b4210-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188  2022-12-11 10:44:36
1  4220657  2ab58790-5e1c-11ea-84a8-633da5152604  2022-12-11 08:21:07
2  4220589  30c06500-2db3-11ed-9a2e-37d9f06d41d3  2022-12-10 23:51:47
3  4220221  fbc1cc90-f7d5-11e8-981e-d16280a3bb5a  2022-12-10 11:41:54
4  4220027  f1989af0-247d-11ed-9b4a-437238555a96  2022-12-10 07:25:59
..      ...
6  4107022  19deed74-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188  2022-09-26 12:32:20
7  4107004  253f4390-36f0-11eb-9146-d10abea54616  2022-09-26 12:22:20
8  4106907  223e5054-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188  2022-09-26 11:35:43
9  4106748  dd819d30-3d74-11ed-a337-45091a2889d9  2022-09-26 10:35:59
10 4106664  d12633e0-3cbf-11e8-9cda-c34368cdd20e  2022-09-26 10:00:25
```

```
authorDisplayName  author authorAvatar \
0      michael      michael
1  Tintswalo M  Tintswalo M
2    Lulama R    Lulama R
3    Moosa M    Moosa M
4  Johanna B  Johanna B
..      ...
6      Ivan      Ivan
7  Nurhaan C  Nurhaan C
8    Rehana    Rehana
9  DAVID A    DAVID A
10  Leandi K    Leandi K
```

```

                                author_id \
0  189b4210-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188
1  2ab58790-5e1c-11ea-84a8-633da5152604
2  30c06500-2db3-11ed-9a2e-37d9f06d41d3
3  fbc1cc90-f7d5-11e8-981e-d16280a3bb5a
4  f1989af0-247d-11ed-9b4a-437238555a96
..
6  19deed74-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188
7  253f4390-36f0-11eb-9146-d10abea54616
8  223e5054-31fa-11e8-83f4-f23c91bb6188
9  dd819d30-3d74-11ed-a337-45091a2889d9
10 d12633e0-3cbf-11e8-9cda-c34368cdd20e

                                review_title review_rating \
0                                Telkom eish             1
1                                Bad service             1
2                                Telkom (9570 Rand To Terminate A ConTract) 1
3                                Telkom sucks           1
4                                BEST TELKOM EMPLOYEE    5
..
6                                Worse customer service ever. 1
7                                The worst service provider 1
8                                HELL with TELKOM: HELLKOM should be their new ... 1
9                                Fraudulent debit from Telkom. 1
10                               Harassment              1

                                review_content ... is_reported \
0  We upgraded our Telkom LTE to uncapped a few m... ... False
1  I use Adsl and I haven't had connectivity from... ... False
2  They are Telling Me To Pay R9570 To Cancel A C... ... False
3  Trying to resolve a billing issue with telkom... ... False
4  I am writing this as one very happy (now ex-) ... ... False
..
6  Canceled a month-to-month contract 3 months ag... ... False
7  So I've got a contract with Telkom which is R4... ... False
8  I am so frustrated at the moment that NO ONE a... ... False
9  Never take any contract with telkom hatfield. ... ... False
10 I am getting almost daily phone calls for an i... ... False

business_reporting author_created_date author_total_reviews_count \
0  None 2014-02-03 2
1  None 2020-03-04 9
2  None 2022-09-06 4
3  None 2018-12-04 2
4  None 2022-08-25 2
..
6  None 2014-03-26 1
7  None 2020-12-05 6
8  None 2015-05-04 15
9  None 2022-09-26 1
10 None 2018-04-10 3

attachments compound neg neu pos sentiment
0  [] -0.6369 0.172 0.828 0.000 negative
1  [] -0.5223 0.153 0.719 0.128 negative

```

2	[]	-0.2960	0.031	0.969	0.000	negative
3	[]	-0.1646	0.038	0.934	0.028	negative
4	[]	-0.9186	0.231	0.731	0.037	negative
..	...	...	...	...	...	...
6	[]	-0.8566	0.076	0.898	0.027	negative
7	[]	-0.8684	0.090	0.910	0.000	negative
8	[]	-0.9180	0.096	0.846	0.058	negative
9	[]	-0.5507	0.091	0.828	0.082	negative
10	[]	-0.7115	0.122	0.844	0.034	negative

[1100 rows x 32 columns]

Machine Learning on the Data-set

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer
sentiment = SentimentIntensityAnalyzer()

# Read the data
df = pd.read_csv('./data/trainingData.csv')

# add the sentiment score to the dataframe add the dictionary rows as columns
df = df.join(pd.DataFrame(df['comment'].apply(sentiment.polarity_scores).tolist()))

df.head()

      comment  sentiment \
0  Not telkpm I pay R519 per month and can't sign...      0
1  Please help me clear my name I can't even buy ...      0
2  Untrustworthy business I was contacted if I wa...      0
3  telkom Have been in a fight with TELKOM since ...      0
4  TELKOM Killarney Looting on Upgrade -10, \nSo ...      0

      review_rating  author_total_reviews_count  neg  neu  pos  compound
0                1                3  0.000  0.966  0.034   0.0762
1                1                3  0.050  0.788  0.161   0.8608
2                1               50  0.072  0.900  0.028  -0.5994
3                1                1  0.203  0.730  0.066  -0.9669
4                1                5  0.099  0.889  0.013  -0.9837

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
train, test = train_test_split(df, test_size=0.2)

# use review_rating,author_total_reviews_count,neg,neu,pos,compound as features
train_features = train[['neg','neu','pos','compound']].values
test_features = test[['neg','neu','pos','compound']].values

# sentiment is the label
train_labels = train['sentiment'].values
test_labels = test['sentiment'].values

# use sklearn to do the classification for KNN
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=5)
knn.fit(train_features, train_labels)
knn.score(test_features, test_labels)

#save model to file
import pickle
pickle.dump(knn, open('./models/knn_model.sav', 'wb'))
```

```

# plot a confusion matrix
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
%matplotlib inline

cm = confusion_matrix(test_labels, knn.predict(test_features))

sns.heatmap(cm, annot=True, fmt='d', xticklabels=['negative', 'positive'])

```

<AxesSubplot:>


```

# plot a graph showing the model at different k values
k_range = range(1, 30)
scores = []
bestAccuracy = 0
bestK = 0
for k in k_range:
    knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=k)
    knn.fit(train_features, train_labels)
    scores.append(knn.score(test_features, test_labels))
    if knn.score(test_features, test_labels) > bestAccuracy:
        bestAccuracy = knn.score(test_features, test_labels)
        bestK = k
print(bestK)
plt.plot(k_range, scores)
plt.xlabel('Value of K for KNN')
plt.ylabel('Testing Accuracy')
Text(0, 0.5, 'Testing Accuracy')

```



```

print(bestK)
print(bestAccuracy)

29
0.8070565232847494

#load model from file
import pickle
knn = pickle.load(open('./models/knn_model.sav', 'rb'))

def predict_sentiment(text):
    sen = sentiment.polarity_scores(text)
    score = knn.predict([[sen['neg'],sen['neu'],sen['pos'],sen['compound']]])
    if score == 0:
        return 'negative'
    elif score == 1:
        return 'positive'
    else:
        return 'neutral'

# print accuracy
print(knn.score(test_features, test_labels))

0.8070565232847494

# use a decision tree classifier with GridSearchCV
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
parameters = {'criterion':('gini', 'entropy'), 'max_depth':[1, 10]}
dtc = DecisionTreeClassifier()

```

```

clf = GridSearchCV(dtc, parameters)
clf.fit(train_features, train_labels)
print(clf.best_params_)
#print accuracy with best parameters
print(clf.score(test_features, test_labels))

{'criterion': 'entropy', 'max_depth': 10}
0.8003910415926058

# use a random forest classifier with GridSearchCV
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
parameters = {'n_estimators':[1, 10]}
rfc = RandomForestClassifier()
clf = GridSearchCV(rfc, parameters)
clf.fit(train_features, train_labels)
print(clf.best_params_)
#print accuracy
print(clf.score(test_features, test_labels))

{'n_estimators': 10}
0.781016708140775

```

Common Phrases

I have ran a small script to compile the common phrases in the dataset quite simple script.

```
import pandas as pd

# Read the data
data = pd.read_csv('data/trainingData.csv')
data

# find the most common phrases from the comment column render that in table
phrases = data['comment'].value_counts().to_frame()

phrases = phrases[((phrases.index.str.split().str.len() < 1000) & (phrases['comment'] > 1))]

from wordcloud import WordCloud
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Create a word cloud of the phrases
wordcloud = WordCloud(width=1600, height=800, max_font_size=200).generate(' '.join(phrases.index))
plt.figure(figsize=(12,10))
plt.imshow(wordcloud, interpolation="bilinear")
plt.axis("off")
plt.show()

# save the phrases to a csv file
phrases.to_csv('data/phrases.csv')
phrases.to_latex('data/phrases.tex')
phrases
```


1-grid Tash communicated very well and was helpful	4
Very good service Very good service	4
Excellent customer s... Excellent customer service	4
Satisfactory Satisfactory	3
Rubyn Excellent service	3
Best service Best service	3
Thank you Tyrone Awesome service from Tyrone	3
Satisfied Satisfied	3
I would like to writ... I would like to write a...	3
Service Good service	3
Excellent Service Excellent Service	3
Great service. Excellent installation and very ...	3
Chantel Chantel	3
The resource you are... The resource you are lo...	3
1-grid Thanks Tash	3
excellent excellent	3
Please delete my account Please delete my account	3
Good so far Good so far	3
Selene Good service	3
Jerusha Excellent service	3
Ok Ok	3
Good customer servic... Good customer service	3
Prince Ndlovu Good customer service	3
Incompetence & poor customer service <p>i have...	3
Great! Great!	2
NO SERVICE <p>The municipality has ignored the ...	2
Great service	2
good good	2
Pleasant Pleasant	2
Service was excellen... Service was excellent	2
Jerusha excellent service	2
Thanks Tyrone Awesome service from Tyrone	2
Nico Good service	2
Absolutely ridiculous! <p>I'm disgusted with th...	2
Happy service Happy service	2
Hellopeter Excellent	2
Disgusting Service Worst cleaning service app e...	2
Pathetic Telkom <p>Since November2016 I have b...	2
Awesome Awesome	2
Great Service Great service	2
Always on time <p>Always on time... TNT must le...	2
Efficient customer service <p>I would just like...	2
Good and friendly Good and friendly	2
Faseeg I'm happy with the service	2
DHL Express - Fantastic Service!!! <p>DHL Expre...	2
Great Service <p>Thank you Kabelo Maluke for y...	2
Thanks Tash Once again Tash coming through in s...	2
I really recommend IG products I have been usi...	2
Excellent service fr... Excellent service from ...	2
Flight Centre secretly charges upto 20% commiss...	2
Incorrect debit order date I Have two contracts...	2
Beaucannon Beaucannon	2
Cancellation Fee <p>We installed a ADT alarm mo...	2
Very good experience Very good experience	2
Great customer servi... Great customer service	2
Unpaid sick leave <p>I was off sick for some ti...	2

1-Grid Great services from Zolani	2
Delete my account Good day\n\nCould you please ...	2
Chantel Thank you	2
Very efficient and h... Very efficient and helpful	2
Clown fest <p>I decided to give this site a try...	2
Effiecient service So far I've had good effieci...	2
Jason Naidoo Good service	2
Fast Fast	2
I would like to writ... I would like to write a...	2
Service is excellent Service is excellent	2
I got an excellent s... I got an excellent service	2
DHL International I said, at this time I disput...	2
Very friendly and ef... Very friendly and effic...	2
Zolani Thank you.	2
They very helpful They very helpful	2
Amanda <div>Good</div>	2
Jerusha Good service	2
Mr Excellent	2
I would like to writ... I would like to write a...	2
Good service Good customer care, easy to reach	2
Good service. Good service.	2
It's excellent It's excellent	2
Great assistance <p>I just spoke to Andrew on t...	2
Exit Exit	2
No thanks No thanks	2
Very helpful and fri... Very helpful and friendly	2
Thanks Tyrone Thank you Tyrone for your assistance	2
Exceptional Exceptional	2
Telkom Rip off Telkom currently has a special ...	2
Kelly Very friendly and helpful	2
EXCELLENT SERVICE!!! <p>I am indeed grateful to...	2
Woodford car hire Excellent service	2
Babalwa Babalwa	2
Acceptable Acceptable	2
The service was good The service was good	2
VEHICLE STRIPPED. <p>My bakkie, a white Ford ba...	2
Very helpfull Very helpfull	2
Very helpful and pro... Very helpful and profes...	2
Amanda good service	2
Fast and efficient Fast and efficient	2
Chantel Excellent	2
Was very good Was very good	2
The experience was o... The experience was okay	2
Yaseen - excellent service Yaseen - excellent s...	2
Thank you Tyrone Amazing service from Tyrone	2
Great assistance Great assistance	2
The agent was very h... The agent was very helpful	2
Removal of review I would like to remove my rev...	2
The experience has b... The experience has been...	2
Efficient Efficient	2
Faseeg Faseeg	2
Best service ever Best service ever	2
Well Well	2
It was good. It was good.	2
Curl error: Connecti... Curl error: Connection ...	2
Jerusha Good service.	2

Pre approval home loan with Ooba. Thank you Kir...	2
Professional service Professional service	2
Jason Good service	2
it was verry good. <p>Ag not much to say everyt...	2
Friendly and profess... Friendly and profession...	2
Amazing service <p>I was totally amazed by the ...	2
Thank you Thank you	2
FIX IT I am giving a 2 Star rating for the wond...	2
Shevone Thank you	2
repairs <p>I booked in my phone for repair towa...	2
I love their product... I love their products	2
Outstanding service by Outsurance <p>My name i...	2
Friendly and helpful Friendly and helpful	2
It is excellent It is excellent	2
SERVICE EXELLENC E THANKS TO ADT N DA SECURITY...	2
Excellent experience Excellent experience	2
Good friendly servic... Good friendly service	2
Friendly staff Friendly staff	2
Bad Bad	2
Good services Good services	2
Rubyn Thank you for assisting	2
Fantastic Fantastic	2
EXCELLENT SERVICE EXCELLENT SERVICE	2
No complaints No complaints	2
Great customer service Great customer service	2
Excellent service <p>I couldn't logon to e-fili...	2
Worse food ever <p>My friend and I ordered nood...	2
The Mattress Warehouse - horrible customer serv...	2
Highly recommended! Friendly, fast, efficient a...	2
Excellent Service <p>Eunice Nhlapo stayed glued...	2
great service great service	2

Acknowledgements

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Raymond's Linked-In

Resources

[ADGSTUDIOS Website](#)

[GitHub Notebooks with Trained Model Ready to Run](#)

[Personal GitHub](#)

[Kaggle Dataset](#)